

Effect of synthetic pyrethroid on behaviour pattern in *Rattus norvegicus*

PRABHU N. SAXENA and DINESH C. SHARMA

Toxicology Laboratory, Department of Zoology, Institute of Basic Science, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar University, Agra, India.

Received January 11, 2000; Accepted March 7, 2000

Abstract

Alterations in the behaviour pattern induced by fenvelrate after acute (1 day) and subchronic (7, 14 and 21 days) treatment in albino rats has been observed. The symptoms of fenvelrate toxicity clearly reflect the expected behaviour changes of a type II pyrethroid which contains a cyno group. Most of the behavioural changes may be due to the effect of cyno group on central nervous system or on nerve transmission.

(Keywords : fenvelrate/*Rattus norvegicus* / behaviour pattern)

Introduction

The development of synthetic pyrethroid is the consequence of our increasing food requirement for rapidly increasing population because approximately 1/3 of total food grain production is destroyed by insect & pest each year. The persistence and continuous application of the synthetic pyrethroids in the higher trophic level of the ecosystem may pose a problem directly or indirectly. The present investigation has been conducted to ascertain the effects of a synthetic pyrethroid fenvelrate on behavioural changes in *Rattus norvegicus*. The important findings of the investigation help us to evaluate the toxic effect of fenvelrate.

Materials and Methods

Rattus norvegicus of almost equal size and weight representing both the sexes were selected from inbred colony. The 96 hours LD₅₀ value (1991 mg/kg body weight) of the fenvelrate was determined by probit analysis of Finney¹. The sublethal doses 381 mg/kg body weight and 20 mg/kg body weight were administered orally for acute (1 day) and subchronic (7, 14 and 21 days) treatments respectively.

Table 1 – Behavioural changes in albino rat after adults (1 day) and subchronic (7, 14 and 21 days) fenvelrate treatment.

Treatment Behaviour	1 Day		7 Day		14 Day		21 Day	
	SC.	DC.	SC.	DC.	SC.	DC.	SC.	DC.
Blinking of eyes	+++	-	++	-	+	-	+	-
Salivation	++	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
Crowding	++	+	+	-	+	-	-	-
Ataxia	++	+	++	-	-	-	-	-
Paresis	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	-
Scratching	+++	+	+	-	+	-	-	-
Convulsion's	++	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
Shivering	+	+	+	-	+	-	-	-
Dyspnoea	++	+	+	-	+	-	-	-
Lethargy	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-

SC. = Spontaneous changes

+++ = Severe

+ = Mild

DC. = Delayed Changes

++ = Moderate

- = Not observed

Results and Discussion

The sublethal acute and sub-chronic doses of fenvelrate effect central nervous system resulting in spontaneous behavioural changes. Rats exhibit overt signs of intoxication after 10 minute of acute dosing.

The spontaneous include general tremors, reduction in activity, salivation followed by blinking of eyes, shivering, convulsions and scratching. Hypersensitivity in response to external specifically to nose and touch followed by brief jerking tremors and stretching of hind limbs was also observed (table 1). Crowding of rats, haunched back posture and immediate thirst for water was also observed. All the above responses appear to be dose related as the similar symptoms have also been observed after the subchronic treatment with low (7 and 14 day) to very low or apparently normal (21 day) intensities after

intoxication. Lock and Berry², Lawrence and Casida³ reported more or less similar behavioural responses in rats and mouse after cypermethrin and other synthetic pyrethroid intoxications respectively.

Rickard and Bordie⁴, Ahmed, *et al.*⁵ revealed similar changes after deltamethrin and cypermethrin in rats respectively. In addition, dyspnoea has also been observed in the present study which may be due to the fact that beside repetitive nerve discharges some other physiological disturbance in the central nervous system, particularly in brain, might have taken place which is probably responsible for the changed respiratory activity. It is suggested that pyrethroids act on the nervous system, causing hyperexcitation and repetitive nerve discharges. Fenvalerate alters the properties of the nerve membrane in such a manner that, when enhanced depolarization exceeds the threshold potential, a second action potential is generated then another and so on. Repetitive discharge are evoked only when negative-after potential exceeds the threshold membrane potential. These findings gain support by the observations made by Verma⁶ who also observed some of the similar changes in albino rat after cypermethrin intoxication. The mechanism of action of pyrethroids suggests that fenvalerate molecules directly plug the sodium and potassium channels at their gate in the brain and probably the observed toxic symptoms like tremors, convulsions, ataxia leading to paresis that appear in the treated rats may thus be anticipated.

The delayed behavioural changes that are exhibited include the facial movement paresis and crowding (table 1). The rats have been observed to be almost normal following late suchronic treatment. It may be due to the fact that rats get acclimatized partially to subchronic treatments of fenvalerate. Further, pyrethroid do induce their own metabolism which results in progressive decrease in toxicity. Costa *et al.*⁷ hypothesized that on repeated exposure to sub lethal doses of an insecticide, signs of poisoning begin but the effects diminish or disappear with continuous successive dosing.

References

1. Finney, D.J. (1971) *Probit analysis*. Cambridge University Press, London, p. 303.
2. Lock, E.A. & P.N. Berry (1981) *Toxi. and applied pharmacology*. 59 : 508.
3. Lawrence, L.J. & Casida. (1982) *Pestic. Biochem. Physiol.* 18 : 9.
4. Brodie, M.E. (1985) *Neurobehav. Toxicol. Teratol.* 7(1) : 51.
5. Ahamed, N., Gupta, P.K. & George, K.C. (1989) *J. Environ. Biol.* 10(3) : 309.
6. Verma, R. (1996) *Effect of cypermethrin on certain brain biochemical parameters in albino rat. - M. Phi. Dissertation*, Dr. B.R.A. Univ., Agra.
7. Costa, L.G., Schwab, B.W. & Murphy, S.D. (1982) *Toxicology*, 25 : 79.